

Exploring the Sign Language Performance of Undergraduate Students at a Pre-service Deaf Teachers' Preparation Program

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Abstract

The ability to communicate through sign language is an essential skill for every teacher in teaching deaf and hard-of-hearing students. This study sought to assess the sign language performance of pre-service teachers of deaf and hard of hearing children using a descriptive research design through conveniently distributed questionnaires. This research aims to evaluate the sign language aspect and helping pre-service teachers' programs designers identify what aspects of sign language needed to be focused on and provide recommendations to improve pre-service teachers' sign language level. The research subjects were undergraduate female students (n= 36) enrolled in a pre-service deaf teacher preparation program at a Saudi Arabian university. This study's outcomes can disclose that pre-service teachers' sign language level needs to be improved and developed; therefore, recommendations are presented for pre-service teachers' program designers to develop learners' sign language performance.

Introduction

The Kingdom of Saudi Arabia is witnessing a tremendous scientific and educational renaissance that began decades ago, especially in education. This was demonstrated in the expansion of the establishment of universities and colleges in various regions of the Kingdom to serve students, researchers, and various community institutions, and in the interest and development in establishing some specialised centres inside universities and colleges that provide services to many sectors of society especially after the announcement of the Kingdom 2030 Vision (Alotaibi, 2020). The mission of universities in the Kingdom is demonstrated to the practical and pioneering contribution to understanding society with its characteristics, issues, and problems, monitoring new educational phenomena, analysing them, and working to provide appropriate solutions to them, such as the establishment of special education departments in Saudi universities considering the Kingdom's concern for people with special needs (Mohammed, 2018). The rational government supports special education programs and schools to fulfil their psychological, educational, health, and social needs (Abed & Shackelford, 2020) and follow modern education principles.

Education nowadays has become based on dialogue, opinion, and discussion using mother tongue, which is sign language for deaf students (Mercer, Hennessy, & Warwick, 2019). Modern education calls for a diversification of communication methods that provide educational content intending to improve educational experiences. To achieve this, teaching methods commensurate with students' age of the nature of the subject, educational goals, learners' level, characteristics, and preferences must be followed and used (Hiver, Al-Hoorie, & Mercer, 2020). Therefore, teachers must undertake several appropriate classroom roles that contribute to the effective teaching method to bring about the learners' desired learning, especially modern methods that focus on the communicative process. Effective communication in classrooms is a requirement for all students, especially disadvantaged children (Bambaeroo & Shokrpour, 2017). Accordingly, it is vital to have effective communication between the teacher and their student in the classroom. This makes school class time more enjoyable and builds a strong relationship between the student and the teacher and vice versa. This will increase the child's absorption capacity in the classroom, feel more comfortable asking questions or ask for help from the teacher (Frey, Fisher, & Smith, 2019).

The deafness hinders oral communication; therefore, this results in the use of sign language by the deaf. Other spoken languages, specifically with body language, use those signals. Sign language is not similar to the English language, as it has its own rules, syntax, synonyms, and idioms. It evolves like other languages and is used by the deaf in all aspects of life (Smith, 2004). One of the primary keys of pre-service special education teachers' preparation program is to develop future teachers to communicate well using sign language with their future deaf students. Communication between the deaf students, each other, or/and the teachers is one of the most critical issues, as it may easier or hinder their integration with those around them. Effective communication is

essential to deaf children's mental health and those around them to break the barrier of isolation and exposed them to active social interaction.

Sign language is an important channel of communication between teachers and students as it contributes to obtaining feedback and contributes to the linguistic and cognitive development of the deaf (Bergen, Lee, DiCarlo, & Burnett, 2020). Furthermore, effective communication through sign language develops a positive relationship between teachers and students who used sign language more coherently (Hall, Hall, & Caselli, 2019; Polat, 2003). Previous studies reported that teachers with high sign language skills and knowledge of the communication modes are highly enabled to develop their students' comfort, learning experiences, and knowledge (Alamri, 2017; Long, Stinson, Kelly, & Liu, 1999; Nikolarazi, 2000). Bergen et al. (2020) and Hayes-Diges (2019) reported a positive influence between learning sign language and psychological compatibility, language abilities, self-esteem, especially if the deaf child may learn sign language in the early years of life. Thus, building communication between the teacher and the student helps the child solve many learning problems, including bullying and absorbing information.

As an alternative way of oral communication, sign language has emerged in the Arab world and documented officially as an independent language. The concerned authorities have made many efforts in using sign language to compose, codify and disseminate it. These efforts have resulted in the Arabic dictionary of sign language, with the same signs of Arabic-speaking countries. Recently, the Saudi Society for Deaf and Hard of Hearing issued the "Unified Saudi Signal Dictionary" (USSD), which include the alphabet and numbers, in addition to more than 2,700 references to original words and phrases. It is one of the critical indicative dictionaries in the Arabs. It includes words and phrases that children commonly use in the learning stage. The intent to unify sign language for the deaf in one country as a communication tool for deaf societies considering the absence of verbal language, is essential to their communicational and social interaction (Lucas, Bayley, & Valli, 2001). Using unified sign language over the country helps them express their views and self-thoughts and acquire necessary knowledge and experiences, which increases efficiency in their social and vocational life and feelings of social belonging (Sandler & Lillo-Martin 2006). However, it should be noted that sign language is related to the environment, so it differs not only from one country to another but also inside the same country from region to another (Al-Fityani & Padden, 2010; Meir et al., 2017). Thus, it is used differently by the deaf societies and the deaf in the same schools or institutions; therefore, the USSD should be used in the KSA.

Hunt and Marshall (2012) emphasised that programs for teaching deaf and hard of hearing students differ from other programs, as it stresses the importance of developing practical communication skills, which cannot be made if teachers cannot communicate through sign language well with the deaf. Therefore, using signs as a method of total communication language can have a positive impact on personal growth and learning, the growth of speech, dealing with others, psychological compatibility, and contribute to the development of language skills, communicating with others, enhancing self-esteem and self-reliance (Herman, 2018; Kholis, Purwobowo, & Ibra, 2020; Leeson, Wurm, & Vermeerbergen, 2014). Considering those mentioned earlier, the importance of studying the unified sign language for the deaf and the teacher's role in applying it in the deaf schools and institutes and programs for integrating the deaf become apparent. From the above discussion, sign language is essential as it is a language of communication among deaf people and hearing people, which confirms its importance and the teachers' role of the deaf in learning it, considering its practice rules as an independent language.

Sign languages use a visual trigger, whereas spoken languages use an auditory space and hearing triggers. Hence, language is a brain-based way of communication regardless of its modality-based. Sign languages have their own rules and grammar of well-formed sentences that pre-service teachers should be aware of and follow. In terms of the type of signs that form the language, the USSD can be divided into three primary levels. The first is the simple signs, which include Arabic alphabets and numbers in fingerspelling. The second level is the descriptive signs, representing shapes, objects, and directions of their meaning. Even people who do not speak sign language can understand its meaning. It is similar to some common gestures used by the speaking society. For example, the sign of the word 'square' can be made by drawing the shape of a square where the sides of the shape should be equal in length, so viewers understand the meaning. Another example is for the verb 'walks' by showing the index and middle finger spread out and pointing at the bottom, simulating the legs, then moving the two fingers to simulate how people walk. The third level is the non-descriptive signs, which include metaphor that does not represent its meaning but can be translated into spoken language. For example, the sign of the word "teacher" is to fold all fingers except the index finger from both hands and place the hands in an X-shape in front of the chest horizontally; hence, the sign of 'teacher' does not represent any hint to its meaning.

From the researcher's previous experience in the teaching field, the researcher believes that the most significant factor contributing to building the deaf and hard of hearing's educational experience is communicating well with teachers using sign language. A number of the indicative concepts in Arabic sign language dictionaries do not achieve the required level of effective communication due to teachers' level of sign language performance, concepts shortage, and lack of coordination and organisation, which hinders the communication and learning processes of the deaf within their schools their normal societies. Accordingly, teachers' mastery of sign language

is necessary for classroom management, especially concerning the human relations that must be prevailed with the learner, the recipient. Therefore, sign language training should be an essential part of the pre-service teachers' preparation program in Saudi Arabia.

Pre-service special education teachers' preparation program, the hearing loss path, in some of the Saudi Universities, in particular, Qassim University, focus on teaching strategies of deaf and hard of hearing children, how to communicate with deaf students, and the difficulties or obstacles they may face teacher during the different learning stages of the deaf learners (Aldabas, 2015). Twenty-four programs existed in Saudi Arabia (Alajlan, 2017). However, these programs are now on hold in admitting new participants (pre-service teachers) into these programs due to several economic and qualification reasons. Importantly, pre-service programs aim to teach participants techniques to modify curricula and prepare them with teaching methods for students who cannot attend general classrooms and meet their requirements (Alnahdi&Anastasiou, 2020). According to Darling-Hammond and Bransford's (2005), pre-service special education teachers' preparation program ought to provide graduates with opportunities to master content and knowledge and related practice skills related to learners' needs, pedagogies, and curricula. They should be able to deal with students with special needs' development within the social context, create, and construe effective instructional and assessment strategies. Graduates of pre-service special education teachers' preparation program can also work on social affairs, health, and labour, organisation institutions that include children with special needs.

In the special education program, the deaf path, at Qassim University, three courses with three-semester credits teach some signs and another course focus on oral communication, concerning lip reading and training the student on applying this method with deaf students. The two sign language courses allowed students to learn and practice sign language with their hearing lectures and professors. The first course focuses on learning and practising alphabets and numbers in fingerspelling, so students are expected to express numbers and alphabets well using fingerspelling. The second course focuses on primary sign language vocabulary (i.e., signs related to colours, countries, religions, family, and measurement units). Although attendees of these programs would work with the deaf in the future, they only get trained on the mentioned aspect of sign language without actual practice with deaf individuals, which seems to be insufficient.

In light of the researcher's attention in the field of pre-service teachers' program in hearing loss and in trying to link theoretical course with skills needed in practice, the researcher noted insufficiency in attention paid to sign language with its standard of rules and principles. Most of the new teachers are using descriptive references in their communication and teaching of the deaf. This led to two systems (the old descriptive sign language for the deaf, the Saudi unified sign language), which negatively affect the academic learning aspects of the deaf students and make a conflict between the various sign language systems. Therefore, the researcher became interested in studying the level of pre-service teachers of deaf learners' performance, possessing sign language, and developing a proposed vision to improve sign language.

As previously discussed, pre-service special education should communicate well using sign language to communicate with their future students effectively. Therefore, this study is designed to assess the sign language performance of pre-service teachers of deaf and hard of hearing children. This would help pre-service teachers' programs designers identify what aspects (the type of sign language) of sign language needed to be focused on and provide recommendations to improve pre-service teachers' sign language level.

Problem Of The Study

The purpose of the present research is to identify pre-service teachers' sign language performance and proposal recommendations on improving pre-service teachers' level of sign language. Consequently, the main research question is:

1. What is the level of sign language among pre-service special education teachers?
2. Whether there are statistically significant differences between the participants' sign language scores in the three domains (simple, descriptive, and non-descriptive signs) related to participants' age, grade point average (GPA), academic level, and the number of received sign language training?

Methodology

Based on the purpose of this study, the researcher used the exploratory methodology. Robson (2002) defines the Exploratory design as a way to find "what is happening" to "seek new insights" toward phenomena without investigating reasons.

Study Sample

Participants were 36 female pre-service teachers enrolled in a bachelor program for special education at the Qassim University in Saudi Arabia. The participants were only females as the pre-service program admitted only females currently. Purposeful participants' selection was used for this quantitative study as the researcher intentionally selects participants, commonly used with quantitative studies (Johnson & Christensen, 2012).

Table 1: percentage and frequency response of pre-service teachers who responded to the research questionnaire.

Variable		Participants (n=36)		
		F	%	
Age	20-21 years old	12	33.3	
	22 years old	13	36.1	
	23 years old	4	11.1	
	24 or over	7	19.4	
Gender	Female	36	100	
Academic Level	Sixth	8	22.2	
	Seventh	26	72.2	
	Eighth	2	5.6	
GPA	4.50-5.00	Excellent	16	44.4
	3.75-4.49	Very good	14	38.9
	2.75-3.74	Good	5	13.9
	2.00-2.74	Acceptable	1	2.8

STUDY INSTRUMENT

An online and self-administered questionnaire was designed to collect the data considering distances caused by the COVID-19 pandemic on attending the university, conducting academic research, and social life. A self-report questionnaire was used to collect data to ensure a high response rate with less time and effort and provide greater privacy and anonymity (Johnson & Christensen, 2012). The questionnaire that has been used in the study includes two sections: demographic questions in the first section and sign pictures in the second section, which included three domains. Simple signs domains (n=10) include numbers and letters signs. For example, the participants are shown a picture of the numbers (8, 12, 6, 1) and some of the Arabic letters (ل-ش-ج-ب-م-س). They were given four options for each of the pictures and asked to select the correct one for the sign on the picture. The second domain was related to the descriptive signs (n= 8). Descriptive signs are a sign language category and include signs representing the word's shape and meaning by itself. The participants are shown a picture of the vocabulary (dance, shy, spins, bicycle, bathtub eating burger, carrying a bag, potatoes) and were given four options for each of the pictures to select the one related to the sign on the picture. The third domain is the non-descriptive signs (n= 8) and includes signs that do not form and the meaning by itself (i.e., the sign cannot describe and clarify its meaning by itself). The participants are shown a picture of the vocabulary (dream, compliments, bathroom, teacher, Thursday, a university, tired, cleaned), then given four choices for each picture and asked to select the correct meaning of the sign on the picture. All the signs were selected from the Saudi Sign language dictionary because the pre-service teacher will work with deaf students in the country and have to use this dictionary with their future students.

The survey was validated using face and content validity. It was presented to six sign language translators to express their opinions on the signs' truthfulness. Agreement on the included statements among the arbitrators was over 80%. Thus, the number of questions at its first design was (34) items of questions. After that, the scale was given to a pilot sample (n=10) of the whole sample. Reliability was measured using internal consistency through Cronbach's coefficient alpha, the items' inter-relatedness within the questionnaire (Tavakol & Dennick, 2011). This method, called internal consistency (half segmentation) using the (SPSS-25) program. The Cronbach's alpha result for the whole questionnaires, comprised of three domains and 34 across the sample, was ($\alpha = .781$). However, due to some reliability risk for some of the questions in domains pointed out by the Cronbach's Alpha (using if item deleted data), eight items of questions were deleted; thus, the total Cronbach's alpha result and the score of each domain were considered to be sufficiently reliable as presented in Table 2:

Table 2: Cronbach's alpha of the questionnaire parts

The domain of sign language	N of statements	Cronbach's Alpha
Simple signal	10	.702
Descriptive signs	8	.595
Non-descriptive signs	8	.677
Total scores	26	.809

Data Analysis

Statistical analysis was completed using SPSS 25.0 software. Before any statistical analysis, normality was tested using the Shapiro-Wilk test. Two values: Simple sign score ($W = .911$, $p < .01$) and non-descriptive sign score ($W = .873$, $p < .01$) values did not meet the normality assumption; consequently, significant differences in these two domains among groups were analysed using the Kruskal-Wallis test. The normality assumption was

met in the other two domains: descriptive signs ($W = .965$, $p = .35$) and the total scores of all the three domains ($W = .976$, $p = .64$): as such, one-way ANOVA were used to obtain the required results. The p-value of less than 0.05 was determined as statistically significant for all tests. The total participants' sign language scores were compared with age, academic level, grade point average (GPA), and sign language training. This was to see whether there are differences between the participants' groups. The total score for each domain was analysed first. Then, the second analysis aims to scan for differences in each of the three outcomes (sign language scores) separately. Data is presented accordingly to the outcome scores.

Results

This study aims to assess pre-service special education teachers' sign ability to recognise some sign language. To answer this question, means, standard deviations, and ranks of teachers' performance on the test were extracted, and the table below illustrates this.

Table 3: To illustrate the means and standard deviations of pre-service special education teachers' sign language scores.

Rank	Demines of sign language	Mean	SD	Level
1	Simple signs	7.1143	1.87509	High
2	Descriptive signs	4.1471	1.81128	Average
3	Non-descriptive signs	2.4706	1.81301	Low
	Total scores	13.7647	4.36278	Average

The means ranged between (7.11 and 2.47) for the three-level of sign language domains. Simple signs came first with the highest means ($M=7.11$, $SD= 1.87$), which is high. It was followed by the domain of descriptive signs in second order ($M=4.14$, $SD= 1.81$), which is on the average, and then the domain of non-descriptive signs in the last place ($M=2.47$, $SD= 1.81$), which is on the low level. The average of all domains was consistent with the difficulty of the three domains, as those domains described before. Taken together, the mean of sum overall scores of the three domains was ($M=13.76$, $SD= 4.36$), which is on the average. In the following, the total scores of the performance in sign language are compared with the independent variable, which includes the academic level.

The second research question was concerning Whether there are statistically significant differences between the participants' sign language scores in the three domains (simple, descriptive, and non-descriptive signs) related to participants' age, GPA, academic level, and the number of received sign language training.

Table 4: Descriptive Statistics for the total score of signs language performance.

Descriptive Statistics				
DV	ID	Groups	Mean	SD
Total scores	Age (years old)	20-21	15.7500	4.33013
		22	13.3077	3.19856
		23	15.0000	2.82843
		24 or older	12.0000	4.97996
	GPA	Excellent	16.0625	3.73218
		Very good	2.99874	13.0833
		Good	8.5000	2.51661
		Acceptable	16.0000	
	Academic Level	Sixth	10.8571	3.62531
		Seventh	14.8750	3.81430
		Eighth	15.5000	4.94975
	N of sign training	Three or more	17.5000	2.12132
		1- 2	14.2308	3.78932
0		13.5556	4.36863	

Table 5: A one-way ANOVA to compare the effect of the age, academic level, and the number of received sign language training on the total score of signs language performance.

ONEWAY ANOVA							
DV	ID	ANOVA	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Total signs scores	Age	Between Groups	68.860	3	22.953	1.444	.250
		Within Groups	461.019	29	15.897		
		Total	529.879	32			
	Academic Level	Between Groups	91.897	2	45.948	3.147	.057
		Within Groups	437.982	30	14.599		
		Total	529.879	32			
	GPA	Between Groups	203.025	3	67.675	6.004	.003
		Within Groups	326.854	29	11.271		
		Total	529.879	32			
	N of sign training	Between Groups	28.627	2	14.313	.857	.435
		Within Groups	501.252	30	16.708		
		Total	529.879	32			

A one-way ANOVA (Table 5) was conducted to compare the participants' groups' differences in the total sign language performance scores. There was a significant effect of GPA on the score of the total score of signs language performance at the $p < .05$ level for the three groups [$F(3, 29) = 6.004, p = .003$]. However, there is no significant effect of age, academic level, and the number of received sign language on the total score of sign language performance, indicating no differences between them.

To find the differences between the groups of the GPA, A Tukey post would be used; however, post hoc tests cannot perform for the total signs scores because one group (Acceptable) has fewer than two cases; therefore, the participant who was in the acceptable GPA group is removed only from the Tukey post hoc test. A Tukey post hoc test revealed that the total signs scores were statistically significantly lower in the very good group (12.38 ± 3.81 min, $p = .03$) and good (8.5 ± 2.51 min, $p < .00$) course compared to the excellent group (16.06 ± 3.73 min). There was no statistically significant difference between the very good and good groups ($p = .17$).

The second research question concerns whether there are statistically significant differences between the participants' sign language simple scores related to participants' variable. The following test was conducted to compare the participants' differences in the simple sign language performance score.

Table 6: To present means, standard deviations, and the Kruskal-Wallis H coefficient for the pre-service special education teachers' performance on the (Simple signs) according to age, GPA, academic level, and the number of received training.

DV	ID	Groups	Descriptive stata		Kruskal Wallis Test			
			M.	SD	Mean Rank	Kruskal-Wallis H	df	Asymp. Sig.
Simple signs	Age (years old)	20-21	8.0000	1.27920	21.88	3.886	3	.274
		22	6.9231	1.44115	14.69			
		23	7.3333	1.52753	17.00			
		24 or older	6.6667	2.16025	15.08			
		Total	7.2941	1.56727				
	GPA	Excellent	7.8750	1.25831	20.81	6.574	3	.087
		Very good	7.1538	1.40512	16.23			
		Good	5.2500	1.89297	7.38			
		Acceptable	8.0000		21.50			
		Total	7.2941	1.56727				
	Academic Level	Sixth	6.4286	1.81265	12.79	2.163	2	.339
		Seventh	7.4800	1.38804	18.56			
Eighth		8.0000	2.82843	20.75				
Total		7.2941	1.56727					
N of sign training	3 or more	9.0000	1.41421	27.75	2.895	2	.235	
	1- 2	7.5385	1.12660	18.38				
	0	6.9474	1.74718	15.82				
	Total	7.2941	1.56727					

A Kruskal-Wallis H test showed that there was no statistically significant difference in the simple signs score between the age groups, ($\chi^2(3) = 3.886, p = 0.274$); the GPA groups ($\chi^2(3) = 6.574, p = 0.087$); the academic level ($\chi^2(2) = 2.163, p = 0.339$); and the number of received sign language training ($\chi^2(2) = 2.895, p = 0.235$). The mean rank score of each group under every variable represented in the above table. Thus, no statistically significant difference between all variables' groups in term of performance in simple sign language scores was reported.

This research also concerns statistically significant differences between the participants' sign language scores in the descriptive domain (i.e., represents shapes, objects, and directions of its meaning) related to participants' variable. The following test was conducted to compare the participants' groups' differences in the descriptive score of signs language performance.

Table 7: Descriptive Statistics for the score of descriptive signs.

Descriptive Statistics					
DV	ID	Groups	M.	SD	
Descriptive signs	Age (years old)	20-21	4.6667	2.05971	
		22	4.0769	1.44115	
		23	4.5000	.70711	
		24 or older	3.5000	2.25832	
	GPA	Excellent	4.8125	1.86971	
		Very good	3.9167	1.16450	
		Good	2.0000	.81650	
		Acceptable	7.0000		
	Academic Level	Sixth	3.0000	1.63299	
		Seventh	4.5417	1.79320	
		Eighth	4.5000	.70711	
	N of sign training	Three or more	4.0000	.00000	
		1- 2	4.4615	2.02548	
0		4.0556	1.76476		

Table 8: A one-way ANOVA to compare the effect of the age, academic level, and the number of received sign language training on the descriptive signs scores.

ONEWAY ANOVA							
D	ID	ANOVA	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Descriptive signs	Age	Between Groups	5.925	3	1.975	.587	.628
		Within Groups	97.590	29	3.365		
		Total	103.515	32			
	Academic Level	Between Groups	13.057	2	6.528	2.165	.132
		Within Groups	90.458	30	3.015		
		Total	103.515	32			
	GPA	Between Groups	34.161	3	11.387	4.761	.008
		Within Groups	69.354	29	2.392		
		Total	103.515	32			
	N of sign training	Between Groups	1.340	2	.670	.197	.822
		Within Groups	102.175	30	3.406		
		Total	103.515	32			

A one-way ANOVA was conducted to compare the participants' groups' differences in the descriptive signs scores. There was a significant effect of GPA on the score of the descriptive signs' domain at the $p < .05$ level for the three groups [$F(3, 29) = 4.761, p = .008$]. However, there is no significant effect of age, academic level, and the number of received sign language on the score of the descriptive signs' domain.

To find the differences between the groups of the GPA, A Tukey post would be used; however, post hoc tests cannot perform for the descriptive signs scores because one group (Acceptable) has fewer than two cases; therefore, the participant who was in the acceptable GPA group is removed only from the Tukey post hoc test. A Tukey post hoc test revealed that the score of descriptive signs was statistically significantly lower in the good group (3.769 ± 1.23 min, $p = .008$) compared to the excellent group (4.81 ± 1.869 min). There was no

statistically significant difference between the very good and good groups ($p = .133$), the excellent group, and the very good group ($p = .189$).

Therefore, data reveal that the GPA of excellent is statistically significant in the score of signs language performance, meaning pre-service teachers with excellent grades in GPA have the highest scores compared to good groups. This means that students with higher GPA are expected to perform well in the descriptive signs, which is expected similar to the total score performance outcome (Table 5).

The following test was conducted to compare the participants' differences in non-descriptive sign language performance scores (i.e., signs usually cannot be understood by non-sign language speakers and need to be translated).

Table 9: To present means, standard deviations, and the Kruskal-Wallis H coefficient for the pre-service special education teachers' performance on the (non-descriptive signs) according to age, GPA, academic level, and the number of received training.

DV	ID	Groups	M.	SD	Kruskal Wallis Test			
					Mean Rank	Kruskal-Wallis H	df	Asymp. Sig.
Non-descriptive signs	Age (years old)	20-21	3.0833	2.10878	19.58	2.187	3	.535
		22	2.3077	1.65250	16.12			
		23	2.5000	.70711	19.00			
		24 or older	1.8333	1.83485	13.08			
		Total	2.5152	1.82211				
	GPA	Excellent	3.3750	1.92787	21.19	7.082	3	.069
		Very good	1.9167	1.37895	14.38			
		Good	1.2500	1.25831	10.13			
		Acceptable	1.0000		9.00			
		Total	2.5152	1.82211				
	Academic Level	Sixth	1.4286	1.61835	10.79	3.945	2	.139
		Seventh	2.7917	1.76879	18.65			
		Eighth	3.0000	2.82843	19.00			
		Total	2.5152	1.82211				
	N of sign training	3 or more	4.5000	.70711	27.00	2.652	2	.266
		1- 2	2.2308	1.83275	15.46			
0		2.5000	1.82305	17.00				
	Total	2.5152	1.82211					

A Kruskal-Wallis H test showed that there was no statistically significant difference in the *non-descriptivesigns* score between the age groups, ($\chi^2(3) = 2.187, p = 0.535$); the GPA groups ($\chi^2(3) = 7.082, p = 0.069$); the academic level ($\chi^2(2) = 3.945, p = 0.139$); and the number of received sign language training ($\chi^2(2) = 2.652, p = 0.266$). The mean rank score of each group under every variable represented in table 4.

Similar to simple domains, no statistically significant difference is reported, but the mean rank shows that students with higher GPA showed better mean rank of performance (3.37) than very good or good groups (1.91, 1.25 respectively), and students in the eighth level showed better mean rank of performance (3.00) than the sixth and seventh group (1.42, 2.76 respectively). This is also similar to the finding of Wohlstetter (2011), who reported that students with a higher GPA earned a higher final course grade than students.

Discussion

This study sought to explore the sign Language performance of undergraduate students who attended a pre-service deaf teachers' preparation program. In this section, the findings are discussed according to their implication on their future to help pre-service program developers to use these variables on their sides. Table 3 shows that participants performed highly on the simple domain and on average for the descriptive sign domain. This was expected as they received two courses on basic sign language as mentioned earlier or because these two categories can be predicted randomly. The first course is provided on the sixth level (term), and the second one is on the seventh level. The courses of total communication methods (1) and (2), as it is called in some universities, does not satisfy the desired purpose as they focus on the foundations and rules of this language and some of the primary and vital terms. Some of the study plan designers think that the skills or knowledge consist of many introductory courses for students, similar to the sign language course, is to start learning path for students, but the development of teachers' skills in sign language takes place in the field by engaging with deaf students. The researcher does not think this is healthy learning as it required communication with the deaf, which cannot be done effectively with a basic level of sign language, as discussed earlier. However, it should be

noted that participants in this study received at least two courses on sign language using e-learning tools due to rustication placed by the COVID-19 pandemic, which has some limitations on sign language learning, as reported by Alawajee (2021).

Besides, data presented in Table 5 reveal that the GPA of excellent is statistically significant in the total score of signs language performance, meaning pre-service teachers with excellent grades in GPA have the highest scores compared to others. This is expected because the higher GPA grade may indicate how students perform in the courses, as the sign language courses are part of the study plan. Similarly, data presented in Table 8 shows that the GPA of excellent is statistically significant in the score of descriptive signs scores, meaning pre-service teachers with excellent grades in GPA have the highest scores compared to good groups. Wohlstetter (2011) studied the association between the academic performance of undergraduate students enrolled in an American Sign Language course and reported that students with a higher GPA earned a higher final course grade than students with a lower grade point average. Thus, students with a higher GPA may perform better in sign language in this study as they tend to perform well in sign languages courses, among other courses.

Table 6 shows no statistically significant difference between all variables' groups in term of performance in simple sign language scores. The mean rank score of the sixth level's academic level is lower (8.00) than the sixth and seventh levels, and it was at the highest among the eighth level. Although this was not a significant difference, and it was with the simple category (only include alphabets and numbers in fingerspelling) and fewer participants in the eighth level, it can indicate that participants developed their skills over time. The number of sign language training courses also indicate increases in the mean rank of the participants, where students who received three or more additional courses show a higher mean rank than those who received one or two courses and who did not receive any additional courses; however, received should be taken into caution as the number of participants in this group is very low.

However, it should be noted that no statistically significant difference in the *non-descriptivesigns* score between all groups (Table 9). Like simple domains, the mean rank shows that students with higher GPA showed better mean rank of performance than very good or good groups, and students in the eighth level showed better mean rank of performance than the sixth and seventh group. This is also similar to the finding of Wohlstetter (2011), who reported that students with a higher GPA earned a higher final course grade than students. Non statistically significant difference between the groups in the academic level variable may be due to the two courses on basic sign language provided by the university, so students in the eighth level groups have completed the two courses; then, they may be performed better than those who did not complete them yet.

RECOMMENDATION

It should be noted that sign language is similar to spoken language except that it focuses on visual learning than other languages that have four different angles equally, speaking, writing, reading, and listening. Using more than one language has become an essential and fundamental matter in teaching children with special needs. Learning a new language, especially sign language, is not as difficult as most people think, but it may take time and effort, as it includes various descriptive signs, signs that can be understood even by hearing people with no sign language training. With the Internet and different means of communication, six main methods of learning sign language are presented.

The first is through communicating with someone who uses sign language fluently. The best way to learn a new language is to use it rather than reading a book or sitting behind a computer screen. Students who learn sign language are only from the dictionary and may not be able to practice; therefore, they lose the language over time and lose confidence. University is recommended to include more deaf people in their hire to offer students in the special education programs the opportunities to communicate with them and practice sign language. Program for pre-service teachers can support social clubs between the deaf clubs and the future deaf teacher to facilitate practising sign language.

The second recommendation is to use sign language daily. Pre-service teachers are recommended to use sign language in the related course, as any language should be used daily to be mastered. The number of sign language courses received in pre-service programs should be duplicated every semester as the current sign language courses are only three (according to the Special education program plan at Qassim University). Therefore, the number of courses seems insufficient as attendees would work with deaf and hard of hearing students in the future and need to use the language daily. Increasing the number of sign language courses would allow faculty and students to apply the mentioned recommendations.

The third recommendation is to focus on the most important things, such as learn some words of greeting in the language before learning the alphabet. Then, participants should learn the signs of the alphabets and letters for the language if necessary. They should collect phrases and signs that used commonly to simple inquiries made by the deaf when met. Most people who fail to learn sign language (based on the researcher's experience) are afraid of making mistakes, whereas deaf society is friendly and understands that the teachers' pre-services programs are learners who may make mistakes.

Social media can be used to practice receiving and understanding signs, especially since most TV channels provide sign language live translation. Learning a new language usually includes substantial video use, so

online social media can provide innovative means of sign language learning to make learning more accessible to interested people (Quinto-Pozos, 2011). Faculty could remove the voice and then ask learners to observe the lip speech and sign language.

Program for pre-service teachers should focus on learning some signs and the grammar of the hand's position and directions in sign language. Some words may be similar in movement, but they differ in the hands' place, position, or shape. Therefore, it is imperative to know the correct location, position, and direction of the sign, as sign language movements start from the area between the ears and the forehead and to the waist area.

The final recommendation is to develop learners' ability to read facial expressions. Sign language is related to the upper torso, arms, head, and face, and to integrate sign language, all these parts must work together; therefore, they should observe and interpret facial expression correctly.

The current practical side did not take its place in the teacher's professional development in line with this era's changes and the stability of professional development plans. The relationship between the professional development institutions for special education teachers and practical educational reality needs to be developed to overcome the two concepts' current isolation and inability. Altogether, some studies indicated that there is an urgent need to establish a national body or council for special education to set standards for the practice of the profession (Brownell, Ross, Colón, & McCallum, 2005), like the Council for Exceptional Children (CEC) in the United States. This proposed council's role is to develop study plans and specifications, facilitate link and cooperation between all parties, monitor the education of the disabled at the national level, and develop in-service training programs for teachers in cooperation with the education centres of existing universities. The Kingdom of Saudi Arabia provides many training programs for special education teachers with all the material capabilities. However, they are not well invested in achieving their goals, which makes spending an educational waste and not an investment of training without a return and an effective product, so such as council can make effective use of these resources through collaboration with a private and governmental organisation, institutions, and schools.

Conclusion

The result of this study indicates that the performance of pre-service special education (the deaf and hard of the hearing path) teachers were high for the simple and on the average for the descriptive signs, but on the low level for the non-descriptive signs in the last place. There was a significant effect of GPA on the score of the total score of signs language performance. The total signs scores were statistically significantly lower in the very good group and good course than the excellent group. However, there is no significant effect of age, academic level, and the number of received sign language on the total score of sign language performance, indicating no differences between them. The study did not find any statistically significant difference between all variables' groups in term of performance in simple and non-descriptive sign language scores. Nevertheless, data reveal that pre-service teachers with excellent grades in GPA have the highest scores in the descriptive signs language performance score compared to good groups. Overall, this study's outcomes can disclose that attendees' sign language level needs to be improved and developed; therefore, six recommendations were presented to help pre-services programs designers help develop attendees' performance.

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